

ADDRESSING THE EFFECTS OF URBAN HEAT ISLANDS THROUGH URBAN PLANNING INTERVENTIONS: A CASE OF DAR ES SALAAM, TANZANIA

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ABSTRACT

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon is increasingly becoming a critical issue due to the adverse impacts it poses to the residents of many cities worldwide; and the extent to which climate change exacerbates the issue. The study sought to assess the adequacy of current urban planning approaches in mitigating the UHI effects in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania by using a mixed method approach. The study leveraged empirical data collected through surveys and interviews, as well as field observations to identify the contributing factors that exacerbate the UHI effects. The results showed that soil impermeability, town morphology, inadequate green spaces, and vegetation cover were significant contributors to the UHI effects, with poor urban planning worsening the issue. In conclusion, the study recommends to address the UHI effects by integration of meteorological data in urban planning and management in conjunction with adoption of green roof and walls, adoption and enforcement of setback regulations and building codes, choice of reflective materials, promotion of co-production, awareness creation and community participation.

Keywords: Urban Heat Islands, Urban Planning, Urbanization

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1. Background Information

Globally, urbanization is one of the most pressing issues in today's world cities. According to United Nation reports, more than 50% of world's population live in urban areas, and this population is projected to increase further by 5050 (United Nation, 2015). Generally, the term urbanization refers to the increase in the proportion of people living in towns or cities compared to those in the rural areas. Therefore, urbanization process describes a shift in a population from one that is dispersed across small rural settlements in which agriculture is the dominant economic activity towards one where the population is concentrated in larger, dense urban settlements characterized by industrial, commercial and service activities (Montgomery, M.R., et al., 2008).

Urban Heat Island (UHI) is among the environmental problems accompanied with the urbanization. Currently, the UHI seems to be one of the most common climate change phenomena in urban areas. This issue has gained much attention from developed countries while African countries are yet to grapple with it on a significant scale (Gyimah, 2023). Furthermore, Hardy & Nel (2015) explained that increased temperature from urban related activities such as industrialization intensify the UHI effects.

UHI is defined as urban areas with higher air temperatures than their surrounding rural areas (Taleb & Abu-Hijleh, 2013). Also, the UHI is defined by Valsson and Bharat (2009), as the concentration of human activities in urban areas that creates an island of heat surrounded by a sea of cooler rural areas. It occurs in metropolitan areas due to the change in microclimate because of an increased population density. Moreover, Taleb & Abu-Hijleh (2013) explain that UHI can be caused by two main factors, microclimate (temperature, wind flow, humidity, solar radiation, and cloud cover) and urban parameters (urban activities such as industries, commercial and residential). As cities grow, urbanization causes less trees and vegetation cover displaced by buildings and roads, more skyscrapers and streets trap the wind, and more heat is released from vehicles and air-conditioners. Thus, higher temperatures, low evaporation, increased precipitation and surface runoff becomes some of the common characteristics of

urban areas (Zekeňáková, et al., 2015). Besides, UHI increases human discomfort and air pollution concentration. Moreover, higher temperatures as one of the effects of UHI increase energy use, especially for air-conditioning in buildings. This increases air pollution and energy costs (APN, 2018).

African countries have experienced UHI effects in urban areas with high housing density, high population density and low levels of vegetative cover (Hardy and Nel, 2015). Stewart & Oke (2012) and Hardy & Nel (2015) explain that areas with high levels of vegetation are cooler and thus have lower UHI effects than less vegetated areas, while built-up areas and densely populated areas are hotter and have higher heat effects. On the other hand; Cavan et al (2014) indicated that residential urban morphology accounts for the largest surface cover and has a potential to alter neighborhood level surface temperatures due to the rise in population. This presents a worrying situation in Africa as cities are rapidly expanding due to the increasing population (Gyimah, 2023) accompanied by uncontrolled and unplanned urbanization (Simwanda, et al., 2019; Chapman, et al., 2017).

Tanzania, like other countries in Africa and the world in general, also experiences the UHI effects as caused by both urbanization and expansion in the cities as well as climate change. The effect is much observed in Dar es Salaam city, which is the main commercial hub of the country and a gateway to the surrounding landlocked countries of Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Zambia and Malawi. Dar es Salaam is located in the tropical climate zone with hot and humid weather, which exacerbates the UHI effect. Due to its proximity to the equator and the warm Indian ocean, Dar es Salaam is the warmest region in the country with annual mean maximum and minimum temperatures ranging from 29°C to 30°C (December- March) and 19°C and 25°C (June-September) respectively (Simon et al., 2023).

Various strategies/mechanisms have been considered that may be used as the protective and adaptation measures to address the UHI effects; such as emphasizing the use of renewable sources of energy, tree planting and vegetation conservation policies, green roofs, cool roofs, and cool pavements (Rupard, 2019). Despite of availability of these strategies, still the urban communities are still suffering from the UHI effects. This study was conducted to recheck the solution of the UHI effects through urban planning interventions. The specific objectives covered in this study include; (1) analyzing the trend of UHI in Dar es Salaam City and (2) determining the urban planning interventions to mimic the UHI effects in urban areas.

2. Research Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach that combines both qualitative and quantitative research. The study was conducted in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania of which Kariakoo ward located in Ilala District was selected as a case study. Kariakoo ward was justified by being the busiest commercial hub in Dar es Salaam city experiencing the highest UHI effect. The ward has a total population of 10,246 residents within an area of approximately 1.86 Square Kilometres. It receives more than 3 million daily visitors for various commercial activities.

The study applied both probability and non-probability sampling. Simple random sampling as the type of probability sampling was applied to obtain the residents to be interviewed since it gives equal probability of being selected with no chance of human bias. With this approach 38 residents were interviewed. On the other hand, non-probability sampling was applied in selection of the key informants. These key informants included community leaders, town planners, and meteorologist. The collected data were analyzed by using computer software such as Microsoft excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to produce figures and tables. Additionally, spatial data were analyzed and visually presented using computer software such as Quantum GIS.

3. Research Findings and Discussions

3.1 Trend of Urban Heat Island in Dar es Salaam City

Dar es Salaam has tropical conditions, characterized by warm and humid weather which is influenced by its proximity to the warm western Indian Ocean. Ilala District in Dar es Salaam City that is highly urbanized with the Central Business District (CBD), it experiences warmer temperature compared to its periphery areas. Kariakoo ward located in Ilala District is more vulnerable to UHI effects. Figure 1 indicates the change in temperature in Ilala district over the period of 20 years from 2000. It reveals that warmer temperature keeps increasing and expands the area of coverage with time. The interviewed Meteorologist revealed that the rise of temperature in the Kariakoo is influenced by factors such as climate change, urban parameters such as population and human activities, urban morphology, and building as well as soil impermeability.

Figure 1: Urban Heat Trend in Ilala District

Source: LST derived from Landsat 8 imagery

The household interview revealed that 49% of the people in Kariakoo said that the hottest hours occur at night, 27% said at noon, and 24% said all the time. This is because during the day, solar radiation heats up the ground and other hard surfaces which is then trapped in buildings, and paved surfaces. The built-up areas' thermal properties cause the accumulation of heat during the day, making them hotter. At night, the heat accumulated during the day is released into the air, raising the night temperatures and resulting in warmer nights in the urban areas, especially in densely populated areas like Kariakoo. About 80% of the respondents revealed that an increase of temperature in Kariakoo is contributed by meteorological factors (temperature, wind, humidity, cloud cover and solar radiation) as well as urban parameters (population and human activities, urban morphology and building condition, and soil impermeability).

3.1.1 Meteorological Factors Contributing to UHI Effects in Kariakoo

Temperature: 100% of the interviewed respondents in Kariakoo are aware of the change in temperature as they admitted that as time goes the area is warmer compared to the years before. Furthermore, the meteorologist revealed that the annual average temperature of

Dar es Salaam city is 20°C with higher temperature from October to March where the peak temperature is experienced in November and February.

Wind: The wind can transport hot air from one part of the city to another, worsening or amplifying the UHI effect. In urban and building design, wind can affect the configuration of the built environment in the urban area, therefore, exacerbating or mitigating the urban heat effect. The Dar es Salaam Master Plan (2015) shows that the city experiences southwest monsoon wind from April to October; northwest in October and northwest from November to March (URT, 2015). The concentration of tall buildings (skyscrapers) at waterfront in Dar es Salaam city hinders the free flow of Seabreeze to the other areas including Kariakoo.

Cloud Cover and Solar Radiation: Cloud cover and solar radiation both influence the formation and intensity of UHI. They affect the amount and distribution of incoming solar radiation on the surface of the earth. “Cloud cover can affect UHI by blocking the sun's rays and reducing the amount of solar radiation that reaches the ground. In cloudy days, less solar radiation is absorbed by buildings, roads, and other impervious surfaces in urban areas. As a result, the temperature in urban areas can be slightly cooler. On the other hand, sunny days with clear skies increase the amount of solar radiation that reaches the earth's surface and can cause UHI to intensify. The intensity of solar radiation varies with time, it is severe in noon due to overhead sun. During this time, the solar radiation is absorbed and re-radiated back into the atmosphere, intensifying the UHI effect.

The impervious surfaces at Kariakoo including concrete, paved ways, and tarmac roads characterized by few green spaces absorb and store large amounts of solar radiation, which re-radiate back into the surrounding atmosphere mostly during the night. This creates a positive feedback loop, where the temperature in Kariakoo continues to rise. This increases the UHI effects in the area which in turn disturbs comfort of the people at night that necessitates excessive use of electrical cooling systems like air conditioners, ceiling fans, and evaporative coolers. In turn, they lead to higher greenhouse gas emissions and higher temperature in urban areas. All the interviewed respondents in Kariakoo revealed that they depend on the electrical cooling systems.

Humidity: Kariakoo being located in the coastal zone, it is experiencing higher humidity of 16.7g/kg that is similar to the humidity of the Dar es Salaam city. The average annual relative humidity is 77.9 per cent and average monthly relative humidity ranges from 72 percent in January to 82 percent in April (URT, 2015). The meteorologist revealed that humidity is direct proportional to the temperature. This implies that the rise of temperature increases

humidity, thus UHI effects. The high humidity in Kariakoo exacerbates the UHI effect by limiting the body's ability to cool down and reducing comfort level.

3.1.2 Urban Parameters Contributing to UHI Effects in Kariakoo

Population and Human Activities: From the 2022 census data, Kariakoo ward has a total of 10,246 inhabitants with an average household size of 4.4 (URT, 2022). Compared to other centres in Dar es Salaam, Kariakoo accommodates the highest commercial activities including the famous Kariakoo market. This makes Kariakoo the most concentrated area in the city, particularly during the day hours. It receives more than 3 million people daily. Meanwhile, about 28.95% of the interviewed households at Kariakoo believed that high population in the ward was the reason behind the high temperature.

With the increasing urbanization, Kariakoo ward has significantly experienced the sealing of open spaces and sealing of the ground, which traps solar radiation, leading to the accumulation of heat. Also, high population and commercial activities in Kariakoo creates traffic congestion that increases emissions and air pollution. Vehicles, with gasoline and diesel engines, release heat, adding to the UHI effects. Busy streets with heavy traffic can trap heat and pollutants in the environment, leading to unhealthy air quality and higher temperatures as discussed by Drapeau et al (2021).

Urban Morphology and Building Conditions: Urban structures and building distribution within a city have a bearing on the occurrence of UHI effects due to their influence on solar energy absorption and wind patterns. Buildings in Kariakoo play a vital role in influencing the occurrence of the UHI effect. Most of the buildings are poorly designed resulting in low energy performance. The roofs and walls of some buildings are generally poorly insulated which leads to a high heat absorption rate. The low energy performance of the buildings results in increased energy demand for air conditioning and other cooling strategies which in turn contributes to increased heat. The built-up area have limited open spaces, vegetation, and permeable surfaces. As it was pointed-out by Hardy & Nel (2015), this increases UHI effects. The area also is characterized by a mix of various functions, narrow streets, and high walls that block air circulations resulting in reduced ventilation. Most of the buildings in Kariakoo ward are 15m high.

On the other hand, from the household interview, 42.11% of the respondents believed that the vertically developed buildings hinder free air circulation and hence contribute to the UHI effect in Kariakoo. The rest (57.89 percent) believe that multistory buildings provide them with cool air during the daytime; thus decreasing the UHI effect. "We always sleep beneath the

multistory building during the day time because the area is cooler compared to the single story” said one of the respondents. This contradicts what was said by the meteorologist who said that multistory buildings influence the occurrence of UHI at Kariakoo since they act as obstacles to the moving wind and air and trap the temperature between them. He also added that the waterfront (Indian Ocean) at Kariakoo is occupied by multistory buildings (skyscrapers) that block the moving wind. This causes the sea breeze not to be felt in most parts of the Kariakoo ward, particularly the inner structures.

Soil Impermeability: This describes how easily water (or other liquids) and air can move through the soil. Soil impermeability in this section has been described through four aspects: spatial coverage and built-up area, road typology, percentage greenery, and extensive pavement.

Spatial Coverage and Built-up Area: The conducted field survey revealed that more than 95% of land at Kariakoo ward is covered with hard surfaces including buildings, pavements, and concrete surface making the area impermeable (Figure 2). Impermeable surfaces retain much heat to the atmosphere making the area warmer. The impervious surfaces in Kariakoo ward have led to creation of a large number of heat-absorbing surfaces that trap heat in the environment.

Figure 2: Built-up area in Kariakoo ward; Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The buildings survey revealed that the construction of the buildings at Kariakoo is against the planning standards. Mostly they are constructed leaving small or none space from

one building to another that limits natural ventilation. This is against the space and planning standard which require for area with building of height ranging from 1-20 storeys, the plot coverage ratio ought to range from 50 to 60% (URT, 2018).

Road Typology: The Kariakoo ward being in orthogonal plan (Grid iron pattern) is accessible by several roads and streets network including Msimbazi street at West side which contain BRT route, the Uhuru streets at the south, Mafia street at North and Lumumba street to the east which connect to Bibi Titi street and Morogoro Road linking it to other wards (Figure 3). These roads and streets are not only paved along the right of way but also are paved along the road reserves to connect to adjacent buildings. The paved or tarmac roads/streets influence the occurrence of UHI (Fokaides et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Road Typology and Condition at Kariakoo; Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Percentage Greenery: The Town Planner of Ilala municipal council and local leaders revealed that the Kariakoo ward does not contain open or green space and the community depend on Mnazi Mmoja open space located at Mchafukoge ward. Figure 4 shows vegetation density and distribution at Ilala District as well as Kariakoo ward. The intensity of vegetation varies with color whereby the dense the vegetation, the dense the vegetation and vice versa. Green spaces act as the breathing point in the settlements thus limited greenery spaces at Kariakoo favors the UHI (Rupard, 2019; Drapeau et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Vegetation cover at Ilala District and Kariakoo ward

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Extensive Pavement: The site observation shows that the Kariakoo area is highly paved which reduces amount of soft landscape. Most of the area are covered by the large-scale of impervious surfaces such as asphalt and concrete for roads, sidewalks, and parking lots. These surfaces absorb and retain heat from the sun's radiation causing an increase in surface temperature. The extensive pavement in Kariakoo prevents the area from cooling down at night, leading to increased energy consumption, decreased air quality, and health risks such as heat stress and dehydration. This implies that the higher impervious surface at Kariakoo, result into leaving little room for greenery and soft landscape, exacerbating the UHI effects.

3.2 Interventions Involved in Mitigating UHI at Kariakoo

The interventions to mitigate UHI effects at Kariakoo are grouped into two categories: local interventions, and planning interventions.

3.2.1 Local Interventions for UHI Mitigation

In 2021 the Green Kariakoo Pogramme was introduced at Kariakoo Kaskazini sub-ward with the aim of regulating and reducing the climatic problems where by UHI was one of them. According to the Ward Executive Officer (WEO), the programme emphasized the residents to plant trees on their plots. The programme was non-funded, and it required individual readiness

and contributions. These led to its failure. Moreover, “the programme focused only on tree planting at plot levels while there are no empty spaces”, said Kariakoo WEO. Also, “not only community participation lagged the program behind, but also the approach was not suitable for the area with compact development, busy and congested like Kariakoo.

Approaches like green infrastructure which focuses on green roofs, green pavement, and wall plants might be good approaches for areas like Kariakoo” said the Ilala Town Planner. On the other hand, the study revealed that the programme failed due to poor awareness creation to the residents. As shown in Figure 5, the interview with households revealed that 84% of the respondents were not aware about the programme. This was one of the main reasons for its failure.

Figure 5: Community awareness about the Green Kariakoo Programme

Community Participation: Community participation is essential for successful implementation of the UHI mitigation initiatives at Kariakoo ward. The study revealed that majority of the community at Kariakoo are not taking part in implementation of the developed initiatives for UHI mitigation. For instance, as shown in Figure 6 about 79% of the respondents who knew about the Green Kariakoo programme did not participate in its implementation. This is a large number of people who did not accept the programme. *“In addressing the issue, awareness and community participation is very important where participatory planning ought to be done before proposing or enacting any kind of intervention. This approach ensures mutual*

interests rather than having the one which is not inclusive and unacceptable by the majority”, said the Ilala Municipal Council Town Planner.

Figure 6: Community Participation in UHI Mitigation Initiatives; Source: Fieldwork, 2024

3.2.2 Planning Interventions for UHI Mitigation

Building Setbacks: Building setback is the minimum distance a building must be placed from the plot boundary to promote open space and prevent overcrowding. Town Planners at Ilala Municipal Council revealed that the use of building setbacks will mitigate the UHI effects by promoting better ventilation. In application for building permits, land developers at Kariakoo provide drawings with clear setbacks. However, during the construction stage they are not adhered to. The approved minimum setbacks for setting a building within a plot for construction in Kariakoo are; 1.5 meter from left and right, and 2 meter from the front and rear sides of the building. These recommendable setbacks are intended to promote cross-ventilation, provide space for emergency services such as fire rescue and allow for shopping movements.

Additionally, it was observed that in some few buildings where setbacks have been considered, the provided space has been occupied by small business activities that hinders addressing of the UHI effects. According to the meteorologist information, building setbacks could mitigate the UHI effects in urban areas by creating green spaces for trees that could reduce peak temperature by 2.05°C and 3.17°C in the respective areas.

Mixed Use Developments: This is the planning and design concept which combines functions such as residential, commercial, and recreational spaces within a single area or building to foster vibrant, walkable communities and land use optimization. Town Planners in Ilala Municipal Council explained that mixed use development concept is one of the planning interventions applied not only in Kariakoo, but also in all urban areas. The concept is more useful in compact development areas like Kariakoo. They explained further that “*mixed-use developments mitigate the UHI effects by reducing the need for long commutes, and releasing the peripheral areas for other developments with greening provisions*”. It was explained further that, “*compact and mixed-use developments might solve the issue of traffic congestion and can create more open space and green infrastructure that can absorb heat and improve air quality*”.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

This article discusses the UHI effects using the case of Kariakoo in Dar es Salaam city. It first described the meteorological factors and urban parameters contributing the UHI effects in Kariakoo and second, the local and planning interventions for UHI mitigation in the area. The meteorological factors contributing to UHI effects in Kariakoo include temperature, wind, cloud cover, solar radiation, and humidity while the planning parameters are population, human activities, urban morphology, and soil impermeability. The study revealed that causes of the UHI phenomenon in Kariakoo include the extensive use of impervious surfaces such as concrete and asphalt, which absorb and retain heat. High-density urbanization and the lack of green spaces further reduce evaporative cooling and tree canopy coverage. Human activities such as high population and concentration commercial businesses contribute to the accumulation of heat in the environment. Additionally, the concentration of people and buildings creates a large heat output; increasing day-time temperature. The absence of natural cross air ventilation corridors and blocked wind by high-rise buildings prevent air cooling. High rate of humidity, in addition to solar radiation absorption and release also escalates the UHI effect in Kariakoo.

The interventions invested to address the UHI effects by using “*Green Kariakoo Programme*” did not work due to lack of community participation. The planning interventions by using building setbacks did not work due to lack of enforcement and poor development control mechanisms. Furthermore, the use of mixed use developments did not work to produce

promising results. Therefore, the following remedial measures are recommended for reducing the UHI effects in urban areas.

4.2 Recommendations

Integration of meteorological data in urban planning and management: Meteorological data such as temperature, wind, cloud cover, solar radiation and humidity are recommended to be integrated in urban planning and management in due consideration of urban population, urban activities, urban morphology, urban greening, soil permeability, road typology, pavements, and building design. This integration is proposed to address the UHI effects in conjunction with adoption of green roof and walls, adoption and enforcement of setback regulations and building codes, choice of reflective materials, promotion of co-production, and awareness creation and community participation.

Adoption of green roof and walls: The adoption of green roof design is recommended to involve planting vegetation on rooftops. Currently, cities around the world are adopting green roof measures as urban planning strategies to mitigate UHI effects and improve their aesthetics. Green roofs are best suited to flat roofs or roofs that slope less than 20%. Also, green wall design provides space for plantings attached to walls as well as gardening on balconies. Adoption of green roof and wall measures can reduce the amount of heat absorbed and radiated by buildings through absorption, cooling, and enhances evapotranspiration, reducing surface temperatures and creating a cooling effect. Figure 7 shows the green roof design proposals in three categories; extensive, semi-intensive, and intensive while Figure 8 shows green building.

	Extensive green roof	Semi-intensive green roof	Intensive green roof
Maintenance	Low	Periodic	Regular
Irrigation	None	Periodic	Regular
Type of vegetation	Moss, sedum, herbs, and grasses	Lawn, herbs, and shrubs	Lawn, hardy perennials, shrubs, and trees
Cost	Low	Average	High
Weight	60 kg/m ² - 150 kg/m ²	120 kg/m ² - 200 kg/m ²	180 kg/m ² - 500 kg/m ²
Use	Ecological protective layer	Green roof	Park-style garden
Thickness of the system	60 mm - 200 mm	120 mm - 250 mm	150 mm - 400 mm

Figure 7: Green Roof Concept; Source: Besir and Cuce (2018)

Figure 8: Green Building Concept; Source: Besir and Cuce (2018)

Adoption and enforcement of setback regulations and building codes: The urban planning measures to address UHI effects includes adoption and enforcement of building setback regulations and introducing effective building codes. Building setbacks are minimum distances to position a building from property (plot) lines to ensure safety, privacy, and proper ventilation within an urban area. The type of setbacks includes (1) front setback, which is a distance from the front property line facing the road; (2) side setback, which is the distance from the side property lines; and (3) rear setback, which is the distance from the back property line. In turn, it increases exposure to ventilation, provide areas for greening and reduces the UHI effects.

Setback regulations create a conducive environment towards mitigating the UHI effects, hence improving outdoor spaces and enhancing energy efficiency. Enforcement of these regulations is key to achieving the desired results. There should be a clear monitoring and follow-up of the regulations before and after building imposition. The enforcement must go in hand with penalties to those who might fail to adhere accordingly.

Introducing effective building codes on the other hand focus on ensuring that buildings follow sustainability guidelines, energy-efficient designs, and the use of materials with low environmental impact. The proposed building codes should support the adoption of green roof

design. Issues like building materials, i.e. building colors, roofs, and orientation can be designed to enable mitigation of UHI the effect.

Choice of reflective materials: Reflective materials regulate the UHI effects by reducing the amount of solar radiation absorbed by the building. Dark colored materials can absorb more heat, making the surface hotter hence contributing to the UHI effect. By incorporating reflective materials, more solar radiation is reflected, making the surface cooler, thus reducing the surface temperature, reducing energy consumption, and costs. Using high solar reflective materials on roofs or wall planes reduces heat gain, improves the insulation of the building, and reduces energy consumption for air-conditions making buildings more energy efficient. The higher the reflectivity (albedo) and emissivity of a material, the lower the risk of storing heat and diffusing it in the atmosphere or inside a building through the walls and the roof. Table 1 summarizes the building materials with their reflectivity characteristics.

Table 1: Building materials with their reflective characteristics

No.	Material	Reflectivity (Albedo)
1	Plaster	~0.93
2	Polished aluminum	~0.85
3	White marble	~0.56
4	Dull copper	~0.36
5	Red brick	~0.32
6	Dirty concrete	~0.20
7	Dark wood	~0.15

Source: Liebard & De Herde (2005)

Promotion of co-production: This involves creating partnerships between different stakeholders including the government, non-governmental organizations, community-based organizations, and the private sector to develop and implement effective measures to mitigate UHI effects. It provides a platform for various professionals such as developers, town planners, architects, civil engineers, and meteorologists in creation of resilient towns towards the UHI effect. These professionals bring important perspectives and expertise to the planning process and can work together to create effective and sustainable solutions. By working together in the planning and design process, professionals can collaborate and develop solutions that are more resilient to the UHI effects. For instance, developers and architects can apply green techniques

such as green roofs and walls for buildings or integrate solar shading with window design to enhance energy efficiency. In the meantime, planners can promote tree planting and public open spaces, while civil engineers can work on the development of efficient buildings or physical structures that adhere to space standards as well resilient to weather patterns. Lastly, meteorologists can contribute to the sharing of weather information with professionals and early warning systems for residents to reduce negative impacts from extreme heat conditions.

Awareness creation and community participation: This involves educating and raising awareness among the public on the dangers of UHI effects and how the community can contribute to mitigating UHI impacts. By encouraging lifestyle changes such as planting of trees at plot levels and along the urban streets, using public transportation, and reducing waste, individuals can play a significant role in mitigating the UHI effects.

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